

ORCHITIS IN ACUTE HEPATITIS B- AN UNKNOWN PHENOMENON

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Abstract

Introduction: Hepatitis B is a common, vaccine-preventable infection with high mortality and morbidity rates worldwide. Extrahepatic syndromes including serum-sickness like syndrome, papular acrodermatitis, polyarteritis nodosa (PAN), membranous or proliferative glomerulonephritis, polymyalgia rheumatica, leukocytoclastic vasculitis, Guillain-Barré syndrome, cryoglobulinemia, aplastic anaemia, myocarditis, pericarditis, polymyositis, juvenile dermatomyositis, pleural effusion have been described in patients with either acute or chronic viral hepatitis B.

Case report: A male of forty years, having non-significant past history, was detected to be suffering from acute hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection, presented with initial prodrome which was followed by development of vomiting and jaundice. His serum bilirubin peaked to 26 mg%. His HBV DNA quantitative load was 663650 I.U./ml with transaminitis. The ultrasound abdomen revealed mild hepatomegaly with gall bladder wall oedema suggestive of acute hepatitis. He was started on antiviral treatment, in addition to other supportive therapy. He responded to treatment within ten days and serum bilirubin showed declining trend and serum bilirubin decreased to 16 mg%. He suddenly developed fever, pain and swelling in right testes which was followed within two days by pain and swelling in left testes. For this surgical consultation was also taken who after excluding other causes diagnosed it to be acute hepatitis B related bilateral reactive inflammatory orchitis.

Conclusion: Our case report is may be first case report of orchitis as an extra-hepatic manifestation of hepatitis B virus infection. There is paucity of data regarding orchitis with acute hepatitis B infection, hence merits vigil for the same by the treating health care specialist.

Keywords: Orchitis, Chronic Hepatitis C, HCV RNA, Transaminitis, Antiviral treatment

INTRODUCTION- Hepatitis B is a common, vaccine-preventable infection with high mortality and morbidity rates worldwide. Extrahepatic syndromes including serum-sickness like syndrome, papular acrodermatitis, polyarteritis nodosa (PAN), membranous or proliferative glomerulonephritis, polymyalgia rheumatica, leukocytoclastic vasculitis, Guillain-Barré syndrome, cryoglobulinemia, aplastic anaemia, myocarditis, pericarditis, polymyositis, juvenile dermatomyositis, pleural effusion have been described in patients with either acute or chronic viral hepatitis B [1-3]. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) related extrahepatic syndromes have been thought to be a result of various immunologic mechanisms [1]. In contrast to the extrahepatic syndromes in acute viral hepatitis which are self-limited, the syndromes associated with chronic viral hepatitis may contribute significantly to the morbidity and mortality because of the persistent viral infection [4]. Hepatitis B virus, unlike other hepatotropic viruses, is a non-cytopathogenic virus that causes injury by immune mediated processes. Immune mediated mechanisms are also involved in the extrahepatic conditions that can be associated with HBV infections [2]. The actual mechanisms by which viruses initiate autoimmunity are unknown. Molecular mimicry is the most popular hypothesis suggesting that viral antigens showing homologies with host antigens generate an immune response that damages host tissue. The viral antigen may not be necessary for perpetuation of the disease, and cross-reacting immune responses can involve humoral,

cellular, or both types of reactivity [5]. We have tried our level best to search in literature about association between orchitis and HBV but till date in literature, no association of orchitis with HBV infection or antiviral treatment for HBV has been reported. Our case report can be the first case report of the same.

CASE REPORT- A male of forty years, having non-significant past history, was detected to be suffering from acute hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection, presented with initial prodrome which was followed by development of vomiting and jaundice. His serum bilirubin peaked to 26 mg%. His HBV DNA quantitative load was 663650 I.U./ml with transaminitis. The general physical and systemic examination was essentially normal, except for scratch marks due to itching. The hemogram showed haemoglobin of 12.2 g/dL, leucocyte counts of 9300/L, normocytic normochromic picture with normal platelet count. The RFT, INR, T3, T4, TSH, blood sugar, autoimmune profile, Viral screen except HBV were all normal. The ultrasound abdomen revealed mild hepatomegaly with gall bladder wall oedema suggestive of acute hepatitis, without any cirrhotic changes. He was started on antiviral treatment with Tenofovir 300 mg, in addition to other supportive therapy. He responded to treatment within ten days and serum bilirubin showed declining trend and serum bilirubin decreased to 16 mg%. He suddenly developed fever, pain and swelling in right testes which was followed within two days by pain and swelling in left testes. For this surgical consultation was also taken who after excluding other causes diagnosed it to be acute hepatitis B related bilateral reactive inflammatory orchitis. He was started on anti-inflammatory medications and within a week his pain subsided completely, tenderness of bilateral testes vanished and size of both the testes normalized. His liver function tests also showed improvement with serum bilirubin declined to 5 mg% and AST/ALT decreased to 120/140 I.U. He is being followed up and has 95% chances of complete resolution from HBV infection, in view of his adult age.

DISCUSSION- Epididymo-orchitis is a clinical diagnosis based on symptoms and signs. The history, eliciting genitourinary symptoms and the risk of sexually transmitted infections (including anal intercourse), alongside examination findings and preliminary investigations, will suggest the most likely aetiology and guide use of empiric antibiotics. Historically, sexually transmitted infections have been identified as the predominant cause for epididymitis in persons younger than 35 years, and enteric pathogens the primary cause in persons older than 35 years. Evidence to support this approach is limited; and age and sexual history are not sufficient for guiding antibiotic therapy alone [6]. The primary viral cause of orchitis, particularly in boys after puberty, is the mumps virus, which can lead to testicular inflammation 4 to 7 days after the mumps onset. Other less common viral causes of orchitis include the viruses responsible for rubella, measles, varicella, coxsackievirus, and cytomegalovirus, with some cases reported after receiving the MMR vaccine. We have already reported Orchitis in association with parotitis in acute HCV patient [7] but in pool of 12000 HBV patients at our center, this is first time we have seen orchitis with HBV infection. It is co-incidence or there is definitive association between the two is area of future research.

CONCLUSION- Our case report is an uncommon extrahepatic manifestation of acute HBV i.e. bilateral orchitis in an acute hepatitis B patient. There is paucity of data regarding orchitis with acute hepatitis B infection, hence merits vigil for the same by the treating health care specialist.

Picture 1- Showing Bilateral Orchitis (Inflamed and enlarged testes) in Acute HBV

Picture 2- Showing Recovery from Bilateral Orchitis – Inflammation resolved and size of testes normalized.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST- The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest and consent was taken from patient as well as parents before publishing this case report.

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